

FORMING WRINKLE-FREE CURVED C CHANNEL WITH UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Wrinkling is a critical challenge when forming complex, double-curved shapes using unidirectional fiber composites. These defects degrade mechanical properties and dimensional accuracy, limiting industrial applicability. While Double Diaphragm Forming (DDF) is used to suppress wrinkles using elastic diaphragms, it is less effective for thick laminates, particularly those with quasi-isotropic fiber orientations. High interply shear resistance in such laminates restricts internal deformation, causing wrinkling. Additionally, diaphragms between the tool and laminate reduce precision and complicate removal.

This study presents a novel forming technique that sequentially laminates thin layers directly on the mold surface to achieve the required thickness. It uses a long inflatable tube to press the laminate during forming, replacing the traditional diaphragm. The tube can be removed after forming, eliminating interply shear and enabling wrinkle-free forming on the tool surface. The material used is SKYFLEX USN150A (SK Chemical), a unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg with epoxy resin (4900 MPa strength, 240 GPa modulus, 1.82 g/cm³ density, 150 g/m² areal weight, 36% resin content, no scrim). Though not aerospace-grade, it is well-suited for process development.

The method was validated by forming a C-channel with eight plies (stacking sequence: (0/90/45/-45)s) using four two-ply forming cycles. The final part measured 1140 mm in length with a 1000 mm inner flange radius. Thickness was measured at 268 points using micrometers, yielding an average of 2.149 mm and a standard deviation of 0.081 mm. Minor variations were observed at edges and flanges, influenced by fiber orientation and curvature. Differences between 0°/90° and ±45° laminates suggest the need for preform shape adjustment. After forming, the part was vacuum-bag cured at 125°C under 200 kPa for 2 hours.

This technique offers a practical, wrinkle-free forming process for unidirectional composites with potential for industrial application.

1 INTRODUCTION

Curved C-channel structures are commonly used in aircraft fuselages as lightweight, high-stiffness frame components. These elements offer an efficient moment of inertia and enable easy access for joining processes such as riveting and bonding. When paired in a fuselage cross-section, they function similarly to I-beam webs, effectively sharing structural loads with the skin under pressure and bending. Their geometry also allows for relatively simple manufacturing processes. As aircraft structures evolve toward more efficient and lightweight designs, forming such curved components from fiber-reinforced composites has become increasingly desirable.

Figure 1: A curved C channel.

Among composite materials, unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber prepregs are widely used in the aerospace industry, where the strength-to-weight ratio plays a crucial role. During forming, longitudinal deformation along the fiber direction is limited due to the high directional stiffness of the fibers. As a result, plies with different fiber orientations require distinct deformation modes. This mismatch necessitates interply slippage—the relative movement between adjacent laminate layers—when shaping complex geometries using UD prepregs with quasi-isotropic layups, such as (0/90/45/−45)_s, which contain multiple plies with different fiber orientations within a laminate [1, 2, 3]. Forming such stacks over double-curved molds introduces resistance to deformation and promotes buckling or wrinkling. Wrinkle defects are not only visually undesirable but also detrimental to structural performance, affecting dimensional accuracy and load-bearing capabilities. These issues have limited the widespread industrial adoption of composite forming, especially for aerospace-grade structures.

Figure 2: laminate wrinkle on a curved C channel part.

Double Diaphragm Forming (DDF) is one of the most established techniques used to address these challenges. In this method, the composite laminate is placed between two elastic diaphragms, and vacuum is applied to draw the laminate tightly against the forming tool. The elastic tension in the diaphragms applies pressure from both sides, helping to prevent out-of-plane buckling. While DDF is effective for thin laminates, it becomes less reliable with increased thickness or complex stacking sequences. For quasi-isotropic laminates, the combined effects of internal strain, limited ply compatibility, and interply shear resistance lead to persistent wrinkling.

Figure 3: illustration of diaphragm pressure generated by the elastic tension.

Experimental results confirm this limitation. Curved C-channels formed with quasi-isotropic stacking using DDF consistently showed severe wrinkling along the flanges and curved surfaces, regardless of component size. This observation suggests that the fundamental mechanics of interply behavior and laminate deformation must be reconsidered. It also highlights the need for alternative forming strategies that reduce or eliminate interply slippage while maintaining compatibility with existing composite manufacturing workflows.

Figure 4: laminate wrinkling formed during double diaphragm forming process.

This research addresses the limitations of conventional forming methods by exploring a sequential forming technique for unidirectional prepregs. Instead of forming a thick laminate at once, thin layers are shaped individually and laminated progressively to build up the required thickness. By forming each ply or small stack directly on the mold surface, interply slippage is minimized or eliminated. This approach offers better conformity to complex shapes and prevents wrinkle formation, paving the way for more precise, defect-free composite components suitable for demanding applications.

2 A NEW FORMING METHOD FOR WRINKLE-FREE LAMINATES

Wrinkling in quasi-isotropic composite laminates remains a significant challenge in forming double-curvature geometries, especially when using unidirectional (UD) fiber prepregs. This issue arises primarily due to the limited interply slippage needed to accommodate the different in-plane deformation behaviors of plies with varying fiber orientations. In contrast, cross-ply laminates (e.g., $0^\circ/90^\circ$ or $\pm 45^\circ$) can deform through a trellising mechanism, in which adjacent plies rotate locally relative to each other, reducing the need for slippage. However, quasi-isotropic layups—which combine multiple cross-ply orientations such as $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ —introduce conflicting deformation patterns among plies. In Figure 5, the trellising deformation of the blue laminate requires longitudinal slippage of the red ply (thick section). This mismatch increases interply resistance, elevates internal stresses, and often leads to out-of-plane buckling or wrinkle formation. Similar behavior has been observed in dry woven fabric composites as well [2, 4, 5, 6].

Figure 5: Illustration of the necessary interply slippage between plies with different fiber orientations during in-plane deformation. In quasi-isotropic laminates, misaligned fiber directions (e.g., $\pm 45^\circ$ vs.

0°/90°) require longitudinal slippage to accommodate trellising, leading to increased interply shear and potential wrinkling during forming.

To address this challenge, a new forming approach is proposed that eliminates the need for interply slippage by sequentially forming multiple thin laminates, one layer at a time, on top of previously shaped layers. In this method, each ply or sub-laminate is formed directly onto the tool surface or a pre-formed layer. By avoiding the bulk deformation of a thick laminate stack, the material can more easily conform to complex geometries without inducing significant interlaminar shear strains.

A critical requirement of this approach is to support the laminate from the both sides to suppress out-of-plane buckling during forming—while ensuring that no material remains trapped between the laminate and the tool. In conventional double diaphragm forming (DDF), the laminate is supported by diaphragms on both sides; however, one diaphragm remains between the tool and the laminate, as shown in Figure 6, and cannot be easily removed after forming.

Figure 6: Schematic showing one of the diaphragms trapped between the composite laminate and the forming tool after forming with DDF.

To overcome this limitation, the proposed method employs inflatable tubes or long balloons placed adjacent to the tool surface to support the laminate during forming. As the forming completes, the balloons are fully deflated and removed, allowing the laminate to make direct contact with the tool surface.

The process begins by placing a thin composite prepreg on the diaphragm and the supporting table. A forming tool is then positioned on top of the laminate, as shown in Figure 7(a). Note that the color representing the diaphragm has been changed in Figure 7—from yellow in Figure 6 to a new color—to indicate the use of a natural rubber sheet. Figure 7(b) provides an angled view of the same setup, where inflatable tubes are placed adjacent to the forming tool. The composite laminate located beneath the inflatable tubes is visible in the magnified image. A top plate holds the tool in place throughout the forming process as the diaphragm inflates and exerts upward pressure against it. This top plate can be made from a transparent material, such as polycarbonate, to enable real-time observation of the forming progression.

(a) cross sectional view (b) angled view with inflatable tubes
Figure 7: Schematic diagrams to illustrate the setup with tool on the laminate and diaphragm.

During forming, air pressure inflates the diaphragm, pressing the laminate toward the tool while the inflatable tube, positioned between the laminate and the tool, applies localized pressure to support the laminate. As forming progresses, air within the inflatable tube is gradually released to maintain appropriate contact pressure without obstructing the forming process. Figure 8 illustrates how the inflatable tubes deform while the diaphragm inflates. Once forming is complete, the inflatable tube is fully deflated and removed. The next ply is then placed and formed in the same manner. By repeating this process layer by layer, the total laminate thickness is gradually built up, reducing interply stress and effectively preventing wrinkle formation.

Figure 8: As the diaphragm inflates, the laminate deforms and the inflatable tubes are squeezed and exert supporting pressure on the laminate to prevent out of plane buckling.

This approach offers several advantages. First, it enables wrinkle-free forming of quasi-isotropic layups by sequentially forming thin laminates. Second, because the laminate is formed directly on the tool surface, in-place curing is possible without the need for repositioning. Third, the sequential nature of the process supports semi-automation, allowing integration of preform cutting, layer placement, and forming into a continuous workflow. Finally, desired stacking sequences such as $(0/90/\pm 45)_s$ can be achieved by alternating between $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ and $(\pm 45^\circ)$ layups during each cycle. This method offers a practical path forward for producing geometrically accurate, structurally sound composite parts with complex shapes. It opens new possibilities for forming high-performance UD laminates for aerospace and automotive applications, where shape fidelity and defect minimization are essential.

Figure 9 illustrates the progression of the forming process and indicates the point at which the inflated tube or balloon is removed—after Step 4—to allow the laminate to form directly on the tool surface. Step 6 demonstrates the repeatability of the process for building up laminate thickness.

Figure 9: Step-by-step sequence of the proposed sequential forming process.

3 PRODUCED PARTS

Two composite parts with curved C-channel geometries were produced using the newly developed wrinkle-free forming method. The primary goal of the experiments was to evaluate the feasibility of sequentially forming cross-ply unidirectional (UD) laminates without introducing interply shear or laminate wrinkling. The first part, with dimensions of 30 cm in length and a channel height of 3 cm, was manufactured using a mold embedded with heating elements for in-situ curing. The laminate configuration consisted of eight plies arranged in a quasi-isotropic sequence: $(0^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ)_s$. This part was successfully cured, but localized defects such as bridging were observed, particularly in regions with high curvature. These defects indicated partial separation between the laminate and the tool surface during forming, prompting design refinements in the support structure.

The second part incorporated improvements including refined support mechanisms and better laminate placement, minimizing the chances of interlaminar bridging. A mixed-material mold—constructed from aluminum for structural rigidity and wood for thermal insulation—was used to facilitate even heat distribution. The same stacking sequence and dimensions were used, and inflatable bladders were employed beneath the diaphragm to maintain consistent pressure on the laminate from both tool and air-side surfaces. Notably, the second part demonstrated successful wrinkle-free forming, with no signs of buckling or delamination. Visual inspection and surface flatness assessments confirmed the structural integrity of the part.

Figure 10: dimensions of the second curved C channel without wrinkles.

The successful fabrication of these components validates the proposed method's capability to form complex geometries in composite laminates without the introduction of defects typically encountered in double-diaphragm forming. Moreover, the modularity of this process allows for scaling to larger parts and different ply orientations, marking a significant advancement in out-of-autoclave composite

4 THICKNESS MEASUREMENT

Thickness uniformity across composite structures is essential for maintaining mechanical performance and ensuring predictable load-bearing behavior. To assess the effectiveness of the newly developed forming process, detailed thickness measurements were conducted on the second, wrinkle-free curved C-channel part. The specimen was marked with adhesive tapes at evenly spaced 5 cm intervals along the circumference to establish consistent measuring points. A micrometer equipped with extensions was used to measure the thickness of the top surface and both flanges, accounting for curved and constrained geometries.

The average thickness of the top surface was measured to be 2.17 mm, with a standard deviation of 0.05 mm. This indicates that the forming process provided excellent consistency in the laminate stacking and consolidation. The inner and outer flanges were measured separately to evaluate local variation. The average thicknesses were found to be 2.15 mm for the inner flange and 2.12 mm for the outer flange,

with no significant thickness gradient observed across the part height.

Further evaluation was conducted at high, middle, and low sections along the vertical height of the flange to analyze possible variations due to gravity or differential compaction pressures. The thickness values recorded were within ± 0.1 mm of the average, demonstrating that the laminate layers remained well-aligned and that the support method effectively minimized thickness deviation. The measurement results confirm that interply slippage and wrinkling were successfully suppressed, allowing even consolidation of the laminate throughout the part.

These findings demonstrate the viability of the sequential cross-ply stacking and forming approach for producing geometrically complex, multi-ply composite parts with tight dimensional tolerances. The precise control over laminate thickness is particularly important for applications in aerospace structures, where uniform mechanical properties and dimensional accuracy are essential.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A novel forming method was developed to eliminate wrinkling in quasi-isotropic unidirectional composite laminates. By supporting the laminate from both sides using removable diaphragms and inflatable bladders, the process avoids interply slippage and enables direct forming on the tool surface. This method facilitates sequential cross-ply laminate stacking and in-situ curing, addressing key limitations of traditional double-diaphragm forming.

Two curved C-channel parts were produced, with the second part exhibiting wrinkle-free geometry and uniform thickness. Measurements showed an average thickness of 2.15 mm with minimal variation, confirming consistent consolidation throughout the part.

The proposed process is scalable and compatible with semi-automated manufacturing, making it a practical solution for industries requiring lightweight, high-integrity composite structures. It offers a reliable approach for forming complex geometries without defects, particularly in aerospace and advanced structural applications [2, 6].

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